

Science and Technology Education and Research in India

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The present status of science and technology education and research in universities and other higher academic institutions has been critically analyzed. Various aspects of teaching in graduate and post-graduate levels, such as course curricula, laboratory infrastructure, library facility, use of modern teaching aids, examination systems, administrative problems, budget cut, selection, recruitment and promotion of faculty members and staff have been discussed. Industry-academy interaction, government aid for development of science, technology and industry, manpower training and research in academic institutions have been reviewed. Finally, some suggestions have been made.

After independence many attempts have been made to improve higher education and man-power training programs in science and technology. The manifestation of such efforts may be seen in the establishment of a number of new universities (totalling about 210), six IITs, a number of regional engineering colleges and similar other institutions. The amount of fund spent by the Central and State Governments on the budget of education (now called human resource development), science and technology has been substantially increased. To generate high quality research and better technology for industry, a number of high profile awards have been instituted by Government as well as private organizations. Various Government agencies like CSIR, UGC, DST etc. are supporting quite a large number of sponsored projects. Nearly five decades have passed since independence, and it is high time to review critically the progress made so far and analyze the success and/or failure in this important area.

Teaching in University

There has been a quantitative improvement in graduate and post-graduate education in India after independence. The number of graduates, post-graduates and doctorates in science and technology has increased significantly making India perhaps the second largest in scientific and technical manpower in the world. However, qualitative improvement has not been enough due to many factors. Proper planning and care had not been taken before sanctioning new universities and similar other institutions. Sometimes important decisions are taken in haste under political pressure. As a result many of the newly established institutions do not have adequate number of qualified staff, competent faculty or even infrastructure. The policy of accreditation of the course based on infrastructure, competent faculty and related aspects is hardly followed in India.

The Faculty

The faculty is the most important element for the growth and maintaining high academic standards in a university. A bright faculty will attract brilliant students who are responsible for good research and other academic output. Very few institutions in India can claim to have bright faculties. The present procedure for recruitment of

faculty members in universities and IITs has failed to select the best and competent teachers. It is often alleged that the members of the selection committees are influenced by the Chairman who happens to be the Vice-Chancellor or the Director, and even incompetent *experts* are chosen as the members of the selection committee. In one of the professorial recruitment of an IIT, it was alleged, that the relevant so-called expert in the selection committee was a B.Sc. with some overseas training in the technical trade! It is, therefore, suggested to constitute a highly qualified Search Committee for faculty appointments, which would locate and negotiate with the suitable candidates for consideration for appointment. The Search Committee will consist of Dean of relevant discipline, Head of the Department, senior Professor in the relevant area, distinguished alumni and Professor of outside university/IIT as well as expert from reputed industry. The Search Committee will also frame a clear objective for assessment of candidates for selection or promotion to faculty positions. The absence of such an objective assessment standard results in manipulative recruitment.

Teaching and professional duty

Teaching is a serious academic duty. For one hour of classroom teaching the teacher has to devote about two to three hours for self-study and checking the students' home-assignments. A university teacher has to take usually about 12-16 hours of classroom teaching and laboratory training per week. This alone would keep him busy for about 48 hours per week. Besides, he has to spare time for other departmental duties and academic activities (Table 1). As a result, the classroom teaching suffers.

Recent fund crunch in the academic institutions has almost forced the teachers to orient themselves as businessmen earning money for their research, laboratory infrastructure, and perhaps, in near future, for part of their salary. A large part of the teachers' time is, therefore, being consumed in negotiations with the fund-giving agencies like DST, CSIR etc.

Many teachers of colleges and universities have engaged themselves in running private coaching classes or conducting other business non-related to education. This has resulted in a drastic reduction of contact hours between

TABLE I—VARIOUS DUTY LOAD OF A TYPICAL UNIVERSITY TEACHER^a (Hour/WEEK)

Classroom teaching	M.Sc./ M.Tech. project supervision	Ph.D. thesis supervision	Research publication	Meeting seminars	Departmental duties ^b	Other professional responsibilities ^c	Total
12–16	2–6	6–12	1–3	5–10	2–5	2–10	30–72

^aThe range of a duty load depends on the degree of involvement, number of students/scholars under supervision, number and nature of publication work etc. of a teacher.

^bDepartmental duties include time-table and examination schedule preparation, laboratory management, procurement of stores, setting question papers, evaluation of theses, reports and answerscripts, students' counselling, training and placement, departmental reports and budget preparation, planning and development work, departmental seminar organisation etc.

^cOther professional responsibilities include organisation of short-term courses and other continuing education programs, professional society's work, journal and book editing, manuscript preparation for books and journals, evaluation of research programs of fund-giving agencies, assessment of personnel for their organisations, participation in expert/advisory committee meetings, consultancy and sponsored R/D work, setting question papers, answerscript evaluation and adjudication of Ph.D. theses of other institutions, etc.

the teacher and the taught. In most colleges and universities, teachers visit their institutions two or three days a week only to take classes. Very few of them are really interested in research or guiding Ph.D. students. Most of the teachers are satisfied if they can complete the prescribed syllabus and least bothered about the understanding and comprehension of the subject by the students. Some teachers dictate old notes or distribute xerox copies of lectures to students. By this way they make more harm than good to the students. It is to be noted that teacher should make the subject interesting and attractive, and initiate brain-storming discussions on the subject in the classroom. He should encourage the students to discover the truth by themselves and apprise them the significance of the theory or concept to solve practical problems, or innovate ideas or new theories.

Semester versus term system

In Indian universities both semester and term systems of teaching are followed. The former is a rapid mode of teaching a course by delivering 3–4 lectures per week for a little over four months, while in the latter the teaching is spread for the whole academic year. More and more universities and engineering colleges are switching from the term to semester system.

In the semester system the comprehension and understanding of the subjectmatter by the students are generally poor due to high speed of finishing the prescribed syllabus. The semester teaching should, therefore, be conducted by giving regular home assignments, arranging tutorials, question-answer sessions, surprise class tests and brain-storming discussions in the classroom involving active participation of all the students. If these are not done, the semester system will lead to students' poor conception and understanding of the subject. The assessment of students in the semester as well as in the term system should be continuous and may consist of the following : results of the two examinations in the semester or term, performance in the class tests, question-answer sessions, home assignments, tutorials and the teacher's assessment of the student, which is based on students punctuality and attendance in

the class, his overall behavior, discipline and personal qualities.

Teaching aids and audiovisual systems

Audiovisual systems such as slide projectors, overhead projectors, public address systems etc. have proved to be indispensable in seminar talks and presentations in conferences. The success of these modern gadgets has encouraged many to use these aids in classroom teaching. But these have not produced desired results in classroom teaching because the scenario in a classroom is totally different. The high speed of delivery by means of modern audio-visuals comes in the way of the students' comprehension. We conducted a study on the various aids of teaching in classrooms. Our students have expressed in favor of the use of chalk and black board in classroom teaching for they find more time to follow and comprehend the lecture.

Assessment of teaching

Teaching by university teachers should also be evaluated routinely by the students on carefully prepared assessment forms, and the personal interview of the representative sample of the students in the class by the Dean and Head of the Department. The report of the Dean on the assessment of teaching of a faculty member may be sent to the department for a detailed discussion by the full faculty for recommendation for appropriate corrective measures. These recommendations of the faculty may be forwarded to the Dean and Vice-Chancellor/Director for discussion in the Academic Council or Senate.

The impact of recent fund crunch

It has been mentioned earlier that the recent fund crunch has already precipitated a number of crises in higher education. Many universities had to drastically cut journal subscriptions and purchase of books and important reports, budget for research and maintenance of existing infrastructure, and even to stop faculty/staff recruitment. The augmentation of laboratory and research facility comes almost to an end. Universities and IITs have been asked to raise their own resources for support, at least in part, of their all activities. Universities in turn have asked their

faculty members to earn revenues as far as possible, and tried to generate funds by raising tuition fees and other charges. If by this way universities and IITs have to earn their total budget, the tuition fees should be prohibitive and beyond the means of most of the students.

In this critical background some suggestions may be put forward for serious consideration. Each university and other institution may generate a corpus fund from the following. (i) Donations from public, industry and its own alumni. Such donations should be exempted from income tax. (ii) Endowments for creating faculty positions, laboratory or other infrastructures from corporate bodies, trusts, public and others. (iii) Incomes from university properties, such as rents, lease fees, selling patents, know-hows, books and other publications. (iv) Incomes from tuition fees, admission and other charges from the students. (v) Earnings from overhead charges of the sponsored and consultancy projects, registration fee of the short term courses, analytical and testing charges for outside samples etc. (vi) Interest from investments in Government bonds, shares, etc.

Similarly, faculty members may be encouraged and suitably motivated to generate funds from sponsored research and development projects, consultancy, short-term courses, manpower training programs, summer and winter semester courses, writing books and technical reports etc. A part of the income from such activities should be paid to the faculty member as an incentive.

The high price of books and monographs and subscription of journals from overseas has offered both a challenge and an opportunity. The local publishers or even the university/IIT may motivate the distinguished faculty to write advanced textbooks and monographs to be published by the University or the local publishers. There is a good prospect for export of such books.

Library facility

Most of the newly established universities have poor library facilities. This has been aggravated further due to the recent fund crunch and abrupt rise of the price of books and the subscription of journals particularly after devaluation of rupee. Even the generously funded institutions like IITs have been forced to cut down drastically the number of journals and books. By proper use of the modern telecommunication network and information storage and retrieval system we could augment the library facilities without increasing the budget.

Regional Research Information Centres (RRICs) may be established in different parts of the country under the National Research Information Centre (NRIC). NRIC will subscribe, preferably by air-mail, most of the important journals and books of all disciplines and serve as the central store-house of scientific and technological information with RRICs as its sub-centres. Universities, technical institutions, research organisations and industry should subscribe the membership fee to the NRIC in order to get

the required information through the rapid electronic telecommunication network systems of NRIC via the local RRIC, or directly. It is important that the proposed NRIC and RRICs should be professionally managed by a private organisation or trust on no-profit-no-loss basis with Government support.

The syllabus and the course content

Needless to mention that modern science and engineering courses, and laboratory programs should be reviewed, revised and updated at regular intervals. Many new academic programs particularly in the emerging fields are interdisciplinary or even multidisciplinary involving the expertise of more than one faculty. Teaching of such multidisciplinary courses demands not only the active participation of teachers of more than one discipline but also the adequate reorientation and self-study of the teacher.

In the above perspective very few university departments have adequate human and material resources to launch such programs. The most important input in modernization of the course curriculum is the motivation of the faculty. Of late, a few universities have tried to revise their course programs, and a few new universities have been asked to start non-conventional courses. But due to lack of competent experts in the faculty, such attempts have shown poor output.

The picture is more gloomy in case of laboratory programs. Even in the reputed universities the laboratory programs are old, out-dated and have little relevance to the industrial activities. The obsolete and out-of-order equipment have not been replaced or repaired due to lack of fund.

The topics for B.Tech. and M.Tech. projects, despite the Nayaduma Committee's recommendation, remain mostly bookish, stereotype, repetitive and are not based on real industrial problems. The graduates and post-graduates of universities and even IITs, therefore, need a thorough reorientation and training of a year or two before they can be utilized effectively by an industry.

The IIT system

It is often said that the IIT environment alienates the students as well as the faculty from the Indian industrial scene, its challenges and opportunities, and although the students after graduation may find a ready market in the West or multinationals in India, they are not better trained for the Indian industry and R/D organizations.

There is some merit in these allegations. Despite generous funding, better and working environment, IITs have largely failed to initiate innovative and original R/D programs resulting in generation of better and appropriate technology for the country. The impact of the IITs on the nation's industrial development and policy planning is hardly noticeable. The reasons are many and varied. Very few faculty members of IITs, like their counterparts in universities, have got adequate first hand knowledge and working experience in Indian industry. The classroom teaching and laboratory programs even in IITs are primari-

ly based on theoretical and analytical aspect of the textbook-type problems, and seldom on real contemporary problems of industry.

The IITs, like universities, have failed to attract their bright students and toppers in the class to the faculty and enrol their brilliant students in their M.Tech. programs. Although the IITs were established to provide technological leadership to the country, the Government of India has so far neglected the IITs in matters relating to framing and adoption of the national policy on science and technology, selection and import of foreign technology for Indian industry, generation and transfer of technology from IITs to industry, and assistance of IITs in assimilation, adoption and improvement of acquired technology by Indian industry including the Government run public sector undertakings.

Despite these shortcomings, IITs have played their role fairly well in running relatively advanced and modern courses even in emerging areas. The contact-hour between the students and the faculty, both inside and outside classroom and laboratory, is appreciably higher than that prevailing in most other institutions. The system of students' assessment is better and well-spread over the entire duration of the course program. The students enjoy some freedom in selecting elective papers, tutorial classes, seminar topics and project areas. The curriculum is updated and revised at regular intervals, and assessment of course programs is regularly held. The library and laboratory facilities are better and the administration is more efficient. This is largely because the IITs are primarily controlled and managed by the faculty.

Research in academy

For advancement of knowledge and generation of technology, the importance of research cannot be overemphasized. Ability to think and innovate is research. And capacity to transform innovation into products is technology. Scientific and technological research must have a clear objective preferably relevant to the need of the society. Even in scientifically advanced countries, for example in USA, more than 80% of the research is applied research with definite goals to achieve. In India, where spending on research is meagre, more than 80% of the research in academy is so-called basic research with poorly defined open-ended objectives, which are old and obsolete. It is not surprising to see that in a teacher's laboratory either the same topic or a related one in the same area has been investigated for the Ph.D. thesis work of the students since the teacher himself started his own independent career as a researcher. The research scholars are asked to collect experimental data as technicians and the supervisor communicates the research papers. In many cases the supervisor finds it more convenient and less time-consuming to write the student's Ph.D. thesis rather than correcting the student's draft.

It is often complained that lack of modern infrastructure and adequate fund is the cause for low-quality research. Let us not forget that our great scientists like Raman or Bose or

Saha or Bhatnagar had neither modern facility nor large funds for their research. Today some of the R/D centres and academic laboratories are quite well-equipped and supported with huge funds. But even these fortunate few have failed to show good output. It is neither the costly facility nor huge fund, but the ability to think and create, is the prime force for research.

In order to improve the research facility in universities and other academic institutions, Government fund-awarding agencies such as DST, DAE, DRDO, CSIR etc. provide large sum of money to project investigators to procure and instal costly equipment in their laboratories. But after the project is over these sophisticated equipment may not be operational because of non-availability of the operator or costly spares. A large number of such capital equipment are thus lying unused and gathering dust in the laboratories.

The concept of Regional Sophisticated Instrument Centre (RSIC) is a step in the right direction to provide modern analytical facility to researchers. But certain additional measures are to be adopted for making RSICs more useful to research. First, the facility of existing RSICs is to be augmented and new centres created for remote places. Second, accommodation is to be arranged in RSICs for visiting scientists/teachers and research scholars. Third, the administration and management of RSICs should be given on lease or on suitable terms and conditions to private parties who will run these centres and offer services at the Government controlled rate. Fourth, each RSIC should have an Advisory Committee comprising of the members from user institutions, Government representatives from DST, CSIR etc., and experts of instrumentation and service. Fifth, big industrial houses are to be persuaded to contribute funds to RSICs and use the facility at concessional rates. Sixth, once this system becomes fully operational, DST and other fund-giving agencies should provide funds for analytical charges and not for procurement of capital equipment in the budget of sanctioned projects.

Industry-academy interaction

The interaction of industry with most of the Indian universities is marginal. Both should come closer for mutual benefit. Industry, small or big, can approach the universities/IITs for a mutually convenient arrangement for R and D assistance and try to utilize the library and laboratory facilities and expertise of the faculty. To achieve success in this endeavour, both the managers of industry and the teachers of university explain their problems, assess the strength and weakness of each other, understand each others viewpoint and objectives, and initiate mutually beneficial collaborative time-bound programs.

Concluding remarks

The record of manpower training and research in the last five decades in Indian universities, IITs and other higher academic institutions of science and technology is not bright. The investment in science and technology by the Government of India has been progressively increased

over these years. The number of universities, R/D centres and similar other institutions has also been increased. Many of the laboratories of such academic institutions and research centres have been made fairly well-equipped and generously funded and some of them compare favorably with those of the advanced countries. In spite of these heavy investments the output is not at all encouraging. The quality of teaching and research in academic institutions has declined over the past years. Generation and transfer of technology from universities and IITs to industry are equally frustrating. Influential scientists and academicians have captured large funds in the name of high profile research and generation of advanced technology. Their performance is dismal and deceptive. The teaching standard in academic institutions has been deteriorated. The course curricula in

most universities are back-dated and have very little relevance to our national need and economy.

It is high time that educationists and policy makers should take a close look and critically analyse the situation. Bold decisions have to be taken. Young and competent teachers and scientists should be encouraged and given authority to take up the challenges of the manpower training, scientific research, and technology generation and transfer to industry. India has no dearth of capable scientists, technologists and real good teachers. But the task of bringing them to the forefront, offering them freedom of work and finally appreciating their good work, lies with the leaders of the society. These young talented generation needs support, encouragement and appreciation.